

ULTRASONIC EVALUATION OF PROCESS DEFECTS IN CNT-BASED CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

As one of the most quantitative nondestructive testing (NDT) technique, ultrasonic NDT technique has been long used for composite materials in various ways until now and has many advantages over the any other nondestructive method from a scientific point of view. Today it has been much progress in instrument technology. To different degrees, elastic moduli, materials microstructure, morphological conditions and associated mechanical properties can be characterized with ultrasonics. Elastic moduli are determined by velocity measurements. Material microstructure can be characterized by velocity and attenuation measurements. Ultrasonic assessment of mechanical properties (strength and toughness) is indirect and depends on either theoretical inferences or empirical correlations [1]. Nevertheless, there is no the standard NDT method for defect evaluation of composite materials. The major reason is that the composite materials cannot be good conductor of sound waves. The ultrasonic principle is based on the fact that solid materials are good conductor of sound waves. The waves are not only reflected at the interfaces but also by internal defects like material separations, inclusions etc. [2]. But composite materials are consist of a number of synthetic fibers and resins and they sometimes work like defect. In this study, we have characterized the defects in carbon nanotube-based carbon/carbon (CNT-C/C) composites nondestructively through ultrasonic technique for the evaluation of spatial variations in material properties that are attributable to the manufacturing process [3-5].

CNT-C/C composites exhibit superior properties like thermal stability, high resistance against thermal shock, high strength and stiffness at high temperature environments. Synthetic carbons

possess a thermostability guaranteed up to 3000 K [6-7]. Because of these characteristics, C/C composites are called to a high temperature material and used in the nuclear industry, the military industry and the aerospace industry demanding practical application and ultra-harsh environment [8-9]. Although workable applications have therefore already been made, there remain problems that are unanswered such as what are the defects in these applications. These unsolved problems cause user to embrace questions to fitness for service. It is worth seeking proper answers to such problems not only for guarantee of the quality but also because of their reliability to real performance. Structurally, composite materials include various defects arising from the fabrication process. These defects will reduce the final mechanical properties of the composite and are the dominant factors of failure.

2 Experimental

Sample is C/C composite included CNT. CNT offers tremendous opportunities for the development of fundamentally new material systems. In particular, the exceptional mechanical properties of CNT, combined with their low density, offer scope for the development of nanotube reinforced composite materials. Sample specimens were prepared with a size of 150mm (width) × 250mm (length) × 7.8mm (thickness) for ultrasonic evaluation. Some of these samples were used for microscopic observation.

To examine the nonhomogeneity of C/C composite, the cross-sections of the C/C composites were preferentially observed using an optical microscope (EPIPHOT 300, Nikon Instruments Inc.). The specimens were mechanically polished using

diamond paste and observed using optical microscopes. Despite the disadvantage such as destructive approach, the optical microscopy exhibit very high resolution. Its results reflect approximatively process condition of test sample even if only the surface can be seen.

After microscopic observation, nondestructive ultrasonic testing is applied for material property characterization. With the results obtained from microscopic observation, the ultrasonic velocity is measured using pulse-echo-overlap method.. Subsequently, the through-transmission ultrasonic C-scans were performed in an immersion method using home-built scanning system (MUTAX 1.0). To guarantee the result of ultrasonic method, we drill a flat-bottom-hole (FBH) in sample as shown in Fig. 1.

With the through-transmission C-scans, FBH and microscopic nonhomogeneities like crack, void and delamination were simultaneously evaluated for quantitative and qualitative assessments.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Microscopic Observation

The cross-sections of the C/C composites were observed using an optical microscope. Fig. 2 shows cross-section image after polishing. The separated images from over-all image in Fig. 2 (a) show the micro-crack, void and delamination caused by fiber-matrix debonding or mechanical stress by developed during fabrication process. The usual objective in NDT is to detect and characterize a variety of discrete hidden discontinuities that can impair the integrity and reduce the service life of a structure. Such discontinuities include cracks, delamination and void in composites as shown in Fig. 2.

Because of poor microstructure, composites may lack strength and it may ultimately exhibit degraded material characteristics. For the reasons, it is important to have NDT methods for characterizing local or global anomalies in microstructure and their associated mechanical property deficiencies.

3.2 Ultrasonic Velocity Measurement

An ultrasonic wave propagating through a material can be used to measure material properties and property alterations throughout the volume of an

object. Many properties exhibited by the surface layer of material are not identical with the behavior of the bulk material. In this respect, the velocity data is essential information needed for ultrasonic evaluation of materials. The velocity can be instantly determined by the following formula

$$v = \frac{S}{\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

where S is the sound path and Δt is the time of flight. Using dry-coupling through-transmission method, ultrasonic velocity of longitudinal waves propagating in the thickness direction was measured [9].

The measurements were repeated three times and the results are shown in Fig. 3. The measured velocities varied between 1.61 and 1.68 mm/ μ s and show quite uniform pattern. In our case, it means that the overall density is nearly same in our specimen.

3.3 Ultrasonic C-Scan

As stated above, C/C composites are a notable advantage but it is also responsible for unintentional wide variations that occur in material properties when input and process parameters are not optimally controlled. Quality control is especially difficult when discontinuities or undesired anisotropy occur during fabrication or when the material contains local resin richness, reinforcement discontinuities, delamination or porosity in critical areas.

Because the quality of composite components is sensitive to the manufacturing process, a marginal process produces a significant number of very poor components and has a dramatic negative impact on quality.

To evaluate the material properties near the surface under the current situation, a high-frequency probe (15 MHz, 12.7 mm, and flat type – Panametrics) was used in the pulse-echo method. Amplitude C-scans were made using the front surface echo as shown in Fig. 4. There is no singular point as we can see in C-scan image and it provides the result of good quality control for surface condition.

The through-transmission C-scan image shows the pile-up image of the non-uniform area in the thickness direction. The result of C-scan image

clearly demonstrates that a high amount of voids, cracks and delaminations causes the poor mechanical property after fabrication.

Fig. 5 (a) shows probe alignment as one of the setup process for applying the through-transmission method. A home-built our system performs automatically probe alignment. In case of the misalignment, we can enormously obtain a different result from C-scan image. Through-transmission C-scan image in the thickness direction is shown in Fig. 5 (b). With 5 MHz, 12.7 mm flat type probe, some FBH was not detected as indicated in dashed circle. On the other hand, the area as indicated in arrow shows nonuniform density in thickness direction.

(a)

(b)

(c)

4 Conclusions

The changes in velocity and attenuation reflect the changes of material property. The ultrasonic technique is a key method for materials characterization. It is widely used for making precise measurements of ultrasonic velocity and attenuation. These two measurements are the bases for accurately evaluating elastic moduli, characterizing microstructure and for assessing mechanical properties.

We showed that nondestructive ultrasonic testing was useful for materials evaluation of CNT-based C/C composites. Ultrasonic C-scan evaluation in the thickness direction was also able to reveal anomalies in the material property. Ultimately, this anomaly is attributed to poor mechanical property. In spite of their problems for more precise application, ultrasonic method hold many advantages over disadvantage.

Fig. 1. Dimensions and locations of FBH for ultrasonic C-scan.

(d)

Fig. 2. Optical image of the transverse cross-section showing (a) overall-image, (b) micro-crack, (c) void and (d) delamination, respectively.

Fig. 3. Results of ultrasonic velocity measurements.

Fig. 4. C-Scan image for the front surface echo

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Through-transmission C-scan result (a) probe alignment for setup and (b) C-Scan image showing FBH and nonuniform area.

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